

Syntheses of Furano Compounds. Part XXIX. A Synthesis of 3-Ethyl- β -brazan: A Case of Alkyl Group Migration in Fries Rearrangement of an Ester of a Mono-alkylphenol

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It is shown that the Fries rearrangement of *p*-ethyl ω -chloroacetate is attended with migration of the ethyl group from 4- to 5-position. Such a migration does not occur with either *m*- or *o*-ethyl ω -chloroacetate or with other esters derived from *p*-ethylphenol. A synthesis of 3-ethyl- β -brazan has been effected.

In a previous communication¹ we reported a synthesis of 2-ethyl- β -brazan, starting from 5-ethylcoumaran-3-one. The latter was unambiguously secured by cyclisation of 4-ethylphenoxyacetic acid. When the synthesis of the coumaranone (IX) was attempted from 4-ethylphenol ω -chloroacetate (I) by the Fries reaction *via* the related *o*-chloroacetylphenol (II), an isomeric coumaranone (III) was obtained. In contrast, 4-ethylanisole (VII) on the Friedel-Crafts reaction with chloroacetyl chloride in carbon disulphide solution afforded the expected ketone (VIII), which on cyclisation provided 5-ethylcoumaran-3-one (IX).

The abnormal coumaranone (III), referred to above, could obviously arise by migration of the ethyl group. We have established that the migration does occur to the 5-position,

because the same coumaranone was unambiguously synthesised by (i) cyclodehydration of 3-ethylphenoxyacetic acid, (ii) by the acid-catalysed cyclisation of the diazoketone (VI), and (iii) from 3-ethylphenol ω -chloroacetate by the normal Fries reaction.

Migration of alkyl group in the Fries rearrangement was first observed by Auwers and co-workers², who observed that in the case of the esters of di- and tri-alkylated phenols, when 2- and 5-positions were occupied by alkyl groups, abnormal products invariably resulted by migration of 6-alkyl group to 4-position or to 3-position, if 4-position was occupied. Further, Auwers and Mauss³ observed that besides 2,4, 5- and 2,3,5-trialkylated phenols, 2,4,6-trialkylated phenol esters also afforded abnormal products, resulting from the migration of 6-alkyl group to 5-, 4- (in which case 4-alkyl group migrates to 3-position) or 3-position. No case of alkyl migration has so far been recorded in the Fries rearrangement with esters of mono-alkylphenols. It has been observed by Auwers and Mauss³ and also by Baddeley⁴ that ethyl group migrates more readily than other alkyl groups. In the case of mono-alkylated phenols, we have, however, found that the migration of ethyl group does not take place in the Fries rearrangement of *o*-ethylphenol ω -chloroacetate or *p*-ethylphenol α -methylchloroacetate. We have also found that *p*-ethylphenol benzoate provides the normal Fries product and we confirm the earlier results of Auwers and Mauss³ that no migration occurs in case of the related acetate.

6-Ethylcoumaran-3-one has been converted to 3-ethyl- β -brazan as before by way of 6-ethylcoumarandione $\rightarrow$ 2-benzoyl-6-ethylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (X) $\rightarrow$ 3-ethyl- β -brazanquinone (XI).

Further studies of the migration of alkyl groups in related systems are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Ethylphenyl ω -Chloroacetate (I).—A mixture of *p*-ethylphenol (9.0 g.) and chloroacetyl chloride (8.0 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 135° for 4 hr. The reaction mixture

2. *Annalen*, 1926, 447, 162.

3. *Ibid.*, 1928, 460, 240.

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 273.

on distillation furnished 4-ethylphenyl ω -chloroacetate (11.0 g.), b.p. 122°/1.2 mm. (Found: C, 60.8; H, 6.6. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires C, 60.5; H, 5.5%).

Fries Rearrangement of 4-Ethylphenyl ω -Chloroacetate.—The above ester (11.0 g.) was treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (25.0 g.), heated in an oil bath (140°) for 5 hr., and left overnight. Next day, the reaction mixture was decomposed with ice, acidified, and steam-distilled. The steam-volatile semisolid product was cooled and filtered to provide 5-ethyl-2-chloroacetylphenol (II) (5.0 g.), crystallising from ethanol in colorless cubes, m.p. 68-69°, showing a violet ferric test. Mixed m.p. with 4-ethyl-2-chloroacetylphenol (*vide infra*) showed depression. (Found: C, 62.4; H, 6.1. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires C, 60.4; H, 5.5%).

3-Ethylphenyl ω -Chloroacetate (V).—A mixture of *m*-ethylphenol (3.0 g.) and chloroacetyl chloride (3.6 g.) was refluxed in an oil bath at 135° for 4 hr. The reaction mixture on distillation furnished 3-ethylphenyl ω -chloroacetate, b.p. 185-86°/7.6 mm, yield 4.8 g. (Found: C, 60.9; H, 5.6. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires C, 60.5; H, 5.5%).

Fries Rearrangement of 3-Ethylphenyl ω -Chloroacetate.—The ester (4.5 g.) was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (9.0 g.) in an oil bath (140°) for 4 hr. The mixture was decomposed carefully as usual and subjected to steam distillation. 5-Ethyl-2-chloroacetylphenol (2.2 g.) was isolated as a solid, m.p. 69-70°, identical with the rearranged product (II), mentioned above. The derivatives (*vide infra*) were also identical.

6-Ethylcoumaran-3-one (III).—A mixture of the above phenol (5 g.), ethanol (50 ml), and sodium acetate (10 g.) was refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The coumaranone was isolated by dilution with water and subsequent extraction with ether. The dried ethereal solution on evaporation provided the coumaranone (4.0 g.), b.p. 115°/2 mm. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 6.1. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 74.1; H, 6.2%). The semicarbazone was crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 215-16°. (Found: N, 19.95. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 19.20%).

6-Ethyl-2-isonitrosocoumaran-3-one.—The foregoing coumaranone (4.0 g.) in glacial acetic acid (45 ml) was treated with sodium nitrite (1.85 g. $\times 4$) at the interval of 1 hr. and was left overnight. Next day, the mixture was diluted with water, affording the isonitroso compound (3.5 g.), which was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 147-48°. Mixed m.p. with 5-ethyl-2-isonitrosocoumaran-3-one (m.p. 156-57°) was 100-20°. (Found: C, 57.3; H, 5.4. $C_{10}H_9O_3N.H_2O$ requires C, 57.4; H, 5.2%).

Hydrolysis.—The above isonitroso compound (2.0 g.) was warmed with HCl. (conc., 4 ml) on a water bath. On cooling, the resulting 2-hydroxy-4-ethylbenzoylformic acid (1.4 g.) was obtained as a water-soluble oil which was isolated with ether. The related quinoxaline derivative was prepared by boiling with *o*-phenylenediamine in acetic acid and obtained in golden yellow needles, m.p. 260°, from acetic acid. (Found: C, 71.5; H, 5.6. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires C, 72.1; H, 5.2%).

6-Ethylcoumarandione.—The foregoing α -ketonic acid was cyclised by heating with acetic anhydride (3 ml) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. on a water bath. On distillation, 6-ethylcoumarandione was obtained as a crystalline solid, m.p. 95-96° (from benzene-light petroleum). (Found: C, 68.4; H, 4.6. $C_{10}H_8O_3$ requires C, 68.2; H, 4.5%).

4-Ethyl-2-chloroacetylphenol (VIII).—To a cold solution of *p*-ethylanisole (5 g.) in CS_2 (50 ml) chloroacetyl chloride (4 ml) was added and the mixture treated with anhydrous

aluminium chloride (5 g.) with stirring at 0°. After keeping the reaction mixture for 2 hr. at the room temperature, anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g.) was added again, the whole mass warmed on the water bath for 2 hr., and left overnight. Next day, CS₂ was distilled and the residue decomposed with ice and HCl. 2-Chloroacetyl-4-ethylphenol was isolated by steam distillation as a solid (2.3 g.), m.p. 50-52°. (Found: C, 60.9; H, 5.7. C₁₀H₁₁O₂Cl requires C, 60.5; H, 5.5%).

5-Ethylcoumaran-3-one (IX).—A mixture of the foregoing compound (2.0 g.), ethanol (2 ml), and sodium acetate (4.0 g.) was refluxed on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The coumaranone (1.2 g.) was isolated as an oil by diluting the mixture with water, followed by extraction with ether. The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 234-35°, identical with an authentic specimen prepared earlier by an unambiguous method¹.

6 Ethylcoumaran-3-one (III) from (a) 4-Ethylsalicylic Acid.—4-Ethylsalicylic acid (0.3 g.) (prepared by Kolbe's reaction with *m*-ethylphenol)⁵ was dissolved in 10% NaOH solution (15 ml) and methylated with methyl sulphate (1 ml) at the room temperature for 1 hr. After adding more methyl sulphate (0.5 ml), the mixture was stirred for 3 hr. more and the solution acidified to provide 2-methoxy-4-ethylbenzoic acid as an oil (0.25 g.), which was isolated with ether. On cooling, the acid solidified, m.p. 29-30°. (Found: C, 66.9; H, 6.7. C₁₀H₁₂O₃ requires C, 66.6; H, 6.6%). The acid (0.2 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by the action of thionyl chloride in benzene solution. An ethereal solution of the acid chloride was added dropwise to a cooled solution of diazomethane in ether (12 ml) (from 1.5 g. of nitrosomethylurea) and left overnight. Next day, after removing ether in vacuum, the *diazoketone* was obtained as an oil. This was treated with glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml), when an exothermic reaction took place, furnishing the coumaranone, isolated in the usual manner, as an oil. The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless, silky needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 215-16°. (Found: N, 19.1. C₁₁H₁₃O₂N₃ requires N, 19.1%).

(*b*). *m*-Ethylphenoxyacetic Acid.—*m*-Ethylphenoxyacetic acid (m.p. 74°, crystallised from water) (5.6 g.) was dissolved in benzene (80 ml) and treated with phosphoric anhydride (17 g.); the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 10 hr. and then carefully decomposed with water and distilled in steam. A small quantity of 6-ethylcoumaranone was isolated, providing a *semicarbazone*; m.p. and mixed m.p. 210-12° (crystallised from EtOH). (Found: N, 19.8. C₁₁H₁₃O₂N₃ requires N, 19.2%).

Fries Rearrangement of 2-Ethylphenol ω -Chloroacetate.—The *ester* was prepared by heating *o*-ethylphenol (4 g.) and chloroacetyl chloride (4 g.) at 130-35° for 4 hr. The *ester* (6.1 g.) distilled at 168-69°/64 mm. (Found: C, 60.8; H, 5.6. C₁₀H₁₁O₂Cl requires C, 60.5; H, 5.5%).

The *ester* was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (12 g.) at 140° for 4 hr. After decomposition, the mixture was steam-distilled to provide 6-ethyl-2-chloroacetylphenol (2.4 g.) as an oil, which on cyclisation with sodium acetate (4.8 g.) in ethanol (28 ml) for 1 hr. furnished 7-ethylcoumaranone as an oil (1.3 g.). The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 215°. (Found: N, 19.3. C₁₁H₁₃O₂N₃ requires N, 19.2%).

7-Ethylcoumaranone was also prepared by cyclising 2-ethylphenoxyacetic acid⁶ (4 g.) with phosphoric anhydride (12 g.) in dry benzene (40 ml). Isolated as usual, the coumaranone was obtained in poor yield, providing a crystalline *semicarbazone*, m.p. 218°; mixed m.p. with the above specimen was 215-18°. The IR spectra were identical.

Fries Rearrangement of p-Ethylphenyl (α-Chloro)propionate.—The ester was prepared in quantitative yield from *p*-ethylphenol (5 g.) and α-chloropropionyl chloride (7.5 g.); b.p. 168°/50 mm. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 6.2. C₁₁H₁₃O₂Cl requires C, 62.3; H, 6.1%).

A mixture of the ester (2.5 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (3.5 g.) was heated at 135-40° for 4 hr. The product was cooled, decomposed with HCl (dil.), and steam-distilled. 5-Ethyl-2-hydroxy-(α-chloro)propiophenone was obtained as a light yellow oil (1.2 g.), which readily cyclised with sodium acetate to provide 5-ethyl-2-methylcoumaran-3-one as a yellow liquid. The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 238-40°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 6.6. C₁₂H₁₅O₂N₃ requires C, 61.8; H, 6.4%). The 2,4-DNP was crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 212°. (Found: N, 16.1. C₁₇H₁₆O₅N₄ requires N, 15.7%).

Fries Rearrangement of m-Ethylphenyl (α-Chloro)propionate.—*m*-Ethylphenyl (α-chloro) propionate, prepared from *m*-ethylphenol and α-chloropropionyl chloride, distilled at 168°/45 mm. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 6.2. C₁₁H₁₃O₂Cl requires C, 62.3; H, 6.1%). The Fries rearrangement of the compound was done as before with AlCl₃ at 140° for 4 hr. 4-Ethyl-2-hydroxy-(α-chloro)propiophenone was obtained as a colorless liquid, which was readily cyclised with sodium acetate to provide 6-ethyl-2-methylcoumaran-3-one as an oil. The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 235°. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 6.5. C₁₂H₁₅O₂N₃ requires C, 61.8; H, 6.4%). The 2,4-DNP was crystallised from acetic acid in beautiful orange needles, m.p. 247°. (Found: C, 56.9; H, 4.3. C₁₇H₁₆O₅N₄ requires C, 57.3; H, 4.8%).

Fries Rearrangement of 4-Ethyl Phenylbenzoate.—The ester was prepared by benzoylation of *p*-ethylphenol and purified by distillation, b.p. 210°/55 mm; m.p. 54-55° (lit⁷. b.p. 328°; m.p. 59-60°).

The ester (1.7 g.) was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) at 140° for 4 hr. The reaction mixture on working up in the usual manner furnished 5-ethyl-2-hydroxybenzophenone as a steam-volatile product, crystallising from petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) in yellowish white rectangular prisms, m.p. 74°. (Found: C, 79.6; H, 6.28. C₁₅H₁₄O₂ requires C, 79.6; H, 6.19%). The *semicarbazone* was prepared by heating the substance with semicarbazide hydrochloride (1 *M*) and pyridine (1 *M*) in ethanol on a water bath for 1 hr. and crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 201°. Mixed m.p. of the *semicarbazone* of 4-ethyl-2-hydroxybenzophenone (m.p. 209-10°; given below) was found to be 190-95°. (Found: N, 14.5. C₁₆H₁₇O₂N₃ requires N, 14.9%). The 2,4-DNP was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 221°. (Found: N, 14.1. C₂₁H₁₈O₅N₄ requires N, 13.8%). Mixed m.p. with the 2,4-DNP of 4-ethyl-2-hydroxybenzophenone (m.p. 235-37°; given below) showed depression of 20.25°.

6. Ipatieff *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 1162.

7. Beilstein, IX, p. 121 (4th ed.).

Fries Rearrangement of 3-Ethyl Phenylbenzoate.—The ester was prepared by benzylation of *m*-ethylphenol and purified by distillation; b.p. 185°/50 mm (lit.⁷ b.p. 322-33°, m.p. 52°).

The ester (2 g.) was heated with anhydrous AlCl_3 (3 g.) at 140° for 4 hr. The reaction product on working up in the usual manner yielded 4-ethyl-2-hydroxybenzophenone as an oil. The semicarbazone was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 209-10°. (Found: N, 14.6. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$ requires N, 14.9%). The 2,4-DNP was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 235-37°. (Found: C, 61.6; H, 4.7. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4$ requires C, 62.1; H, 4.4%).

3-Ethyl- β -brazanquinone (XI).—On condensing 6-ethylcoumarandione (0.5 g.) with phenacyl bromide (0.5 g.) in ethanolic sodium ethoxide (from sodium, 0.07 g.) for 3 hr., ethyl-2-benzoyl-6-ethylcoumarone-3-carboxylate was obtained as a gum, which on hydrolysis provided 2-benzoyl-6-ethylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (0.25 g.), m.p. 88-90°, which was best purified through the sparingly soluble sodium salt. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 5.0. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 73.5; H, 4.8%).

The acid (0.2 g.) was converted to the acid chloride by the action of thionyl chloride in benzene. After removing the solvent in vacuum, the acid chloride was dissolved in CS_2 (5 ml) and treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1 g.) at 0°. After 10 hr., CS_2 was removed by decantation and then decomposed with iced HCl. 3-Ethyl- β -brazanquinone (0.1 g.) was separated and purified by chromatography over alumina, m.p. 222-23° (from acetic acid). (Found: C, 78.0; H, 4.9. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 78.5; H, 4.3%). Reductive acetylation with zinc dust and acetic anhydride afforded 3-ethyl-6, 11-diacetoxy- β -brazan, crystallising in colorless needles, m.p. 190-92° (from acetic acid). (Found: C, 80.2; H, 5.6. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 80.0; H, 5.5%).

3-Ethyl- β -brazan.—The above quinone (0.08 g.) was refluxed with hydriodic acid (3 ml) for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with water, decolorised with sulphurous acid, and the product collected to furnish 3-ethyl- β -brazan, crystallising from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 290-92°. (Found: C, 88.2; H, 5.8. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 87.8; H, 5.7%).